

User Education, Information Resources Accessibility and Quality Service Delivery in Medical University Libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Quality Service Delivery (QSD) is crucial for librarians to meet users' needs. However, medical university libraries often suffer from poor QSD, as evidenced by inconvenient operation hours, poor equipment, lack of knowledge in answering queries, and delays in user requests. User Education (UE) and Information Resources Accessibility (IRA) have been identified as key enhancers for QSD.

Methodology: This study employed a survey research design targeting 3,761 medical students in medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria. Using Taro Yamane's formula, a sample size of 361 was determined. Stratified random sampling was used to select respondents. Data were collected via a structured and validated questionnaire, with a response rate of 93.07%. Cronbach's alpha values ranged from 0.71 to 0.92. Data analysis was conducted using inferential statistics (simple and multiple regression) at a 5% significance level.

Findings/Results: The results indicated that UE and IRA jointly significantly influenced QSD (Adj.R2 = 0.37, $F(7, 333) = 29.45$, $p < 0.05$). Specifically, UE (Adj.R2 = 0.32, $F(4,$

330) = 40.92, $p < 0.05$) and IRA (Adj.R2 = 0.33, $F(3, 331) = 56.77$, $p < 0.05$) both had positive significant influences on QSD.

Implications: The findings can be generalized to other medical libraries, offering insights for improving UE and IRA to enhance QSD nationwide.

Conclusion: The study concludes that enhancing UE and IRA can significantly improve QSD in medical university libraries.

Recommendations: The study recommends that university management continue to provide training and development opportunities for staff to enhance reliability, responsiveness, and a convenient environment, ultimately delivering quality services in Plateau and Nasarawa States.

Keywords: Information resources, Information resources accessibility, Medical students, Quality service delivery, Services delivery, User education, University libraries

Introduction

Quality service delivery means attending to and answering every user's question as accurately, completely, and as soon as possible (Sharma, 2001). Quality service delivery is seen as a strategic tool for positioning and achieving operational efficiency and enhancing performance. Adamu (2017) asserted that quality service delivery is seen as bridging the gap between user expectations and the actual service provided. However, according to Carvalho and Dominguez (2012), the primary characteristics defining the quality of library services are excellence, conformity to specifications, and the capacity to meet or exceed customer expectations. Agoh and Omekwu (2022) explained that quality service delivery encompasses mechanisms that interact to affect the effectiveness of library and information services. However, delivering information to everyone requires a well-equipped library and well-packaged information services delivery, particularly in medical university libraries (Akpan-Ataha, 2013; Edidiong et al., 2015). Quality service delivery involves the work librarians do to answer users' questions and satisfy their general information needs, including tasks such as abstracting information, interlibrary loans, and user education services etc

Providing quality service is about helping to define and satisfy user needs by building users' confidence in using information retrieval systems and making the whole activity of working with the library staff a pleasurable experience (Ashok, 2007). Institutions must

meet their users' expectations on how to access information by providing current awareness services, reference services, bibliographic services, audiovisual services, borrowing services, internet services, and shelf-labeling services that can boost clients' happiness and long-term profitability in their studies. However, regarding confidence building to users' service through quality service delivery, Lujam and Armando (2017) suggest that a relationship between resource service delivery and the value created as a result of an organization's resources to meet users' expectations

Quality service delivery helps communicate the holdings of the medical library resources as an institution performing to provide service to medical students. Therefore, delivering high-quality services is very significant because successful verbal and non-verbal communication exchange requires common willingness and logic to describe how well material services are provided to users of medical libraries, especially in Plateau and Nasarawa State University. For this study, the provision of quality services in medical university libraries is operationally defined as the extent to which library users receive, understand, and benefit from the information and services provided (Jones, 2005; Sengupta et al., 2000).

Quality service delivery to users can achieve its objectives in medical university libraries when librarians possess comprehensive knowledge of user education, enabling them to effectively provide library resources to users. User education encompasses informing, advising, assisting, and training library users to identify, recognize, comprehend, and effectively utilize library information resources for their benefit. Oyeyemi and Adayi (2022) described user education as a program developed to inform and influence attitudes about library usage, inspiring users to acquire knowledge about library resources, which is essential for individual, group, and societal advancement. Nagaraju (2009) defined user education as educational programs designed to empower library patrons with the confidence to locate and utilize the materials or resources they require.

User education can be supported with indicators such as library orientation, library tour, bibliographic instruction, and virtual talk. Library orientation enables librarians provide an opportunity to introduce new students and other library users to the complexity of university information materials (Agyen, 2008; Bashorun et al., 2020). The literacy skills basis of library orientation helps librarians measure user education. Library orientation is a program designed to inform users about library resources, activities, and services offered in the library. Library tours. is seen as situation where users are taken around to be shown some basic research skills. Users take turns highlighting appropriate research materials. In the case of bibliography instruction, users are informed to be abreast of all

relevant information about repackaging their information. Saunders (2003) argued that the goal of instruction in bibliography is to prepare users to utilize libraries responsibly and independently. Bibliography instruction enables users to know the search materials in a particular subject area. It helps users understand the description of the physical organization of information resources. Virtual talks serve as key indicators for user education. It refers to any remote communication where computer-based connections are joined between two or more persons, and people integrate with various facets of daily life and rely on it. It forms a knowledge-sharing spread into the field of libraries, whereby users are educated

User education can enhance to attend desired objectives in medical university libraries worldwide, particularly in Plateau and Nasarawa States, if librarians possess knowledge about the understanding of information resources accessibility. It refers to how simple it is for service providers to go from one point to another to locate and utilize the information resources or library materials. It refers to materials that offer information in print and digital media accessible to users. Sunday and Yacob (2009) defined it as materials that include information in print and non-print media accessible to library users.

The usefulness of materials to the users in this study aims to identify and articulate, comprehend, influence, and, where necessary, remove the barriers that prevent users from attaining their stated goals. Nwachukwi et al. (2014) and Vickery (2004) noted that the usefulness of material is good for management and is necessary to maximize user satisfaction through useful resources of information used in the library to be taken into account as the users' access to the resources and their uses.

The types of information resources accessible in medical libraries today can raise user hopes and encourage frequent visits to library resources. These resources are categorized into two types: print and non-print materials. Print materials include textbooks, journals, newspapers, and magazines. Non-print or electronic materials encompass CD-ROMs, the Internet, Medline, Popline, Hinari, Index Medicus, and others. It is essential to recognize that information resources comprise collections of recorded information, including printed materials like books, periodicals, reference materials, manuscripts, magazines, theses, and gazettes, as well as non-print materials like magnetic tapes, slides, videotapes, and data stored on electronic media like discs and CD-ROMs (Abubakar, 2020; Clifford & Olurotim, 2014).

Access methods according to Abubakar (2020), are crucial indicators of user satisfaction with library resources. Key access methods include internet facilities in the library and

employing qualified staff to sustain library resources. Oladape et al. (2021) reported that online information searching techniques require a reliable internet service provider and personnel with knowledge and experience to provide accessible resources. Several studies have investigated variables related to this study. However, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, none have examined the specific combination of variables. Therefore, the study aims to investigate the influence of user education, information resources accessibility, and quality service delivery in medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Adamu (2017) asserted that service quality delivery is seen as bridging the gap between user expectations and the actual service provided. In other words, service quality delivery is seen as a strategic tool for positioning and achieving operational efficiency and enhancing performance (Adamu, 2017). According to Edeole (2019), quality service "includes all bundles of services that the library provides to users to support and advance the objectives of the parent institution. Agoh and Omekwu (2021) considered quality service delivery as a set of mechanisms whose interactions affect the effectiveness of library and information services. Quality service delivery is a phenomenon that takes into account consumers' expectations and positive impressions of the services provided (Erkan et al., 2014; Kucukaltan, 2007).

Philip (2015). Oyeyemi and Adayi (2022) described library user education as being developed to inform and influence attitudes about library usage and, more importantly, to inspire their quest for knowledge, which is essential for the advancement of individuals and societies. Nagaraju (2009) says user education consists of educational programs created for patrons to give them the confidence to find and use the information required. Ejiroghene (2020) and Marshall et al. (2007) indicated that user education is library instruction programs run in the library that have the advantage of introducing learners to the physical space of the library as well as intangible goods.

According to Aliyu (2015), it composed of a range of components that allow for the storage, retrieval, and dissemination of information for use. Similarly, Bitagi and Garba (2014) and Usman (2016) describe information resources accessibility as a collection of tools and supplies acquired by a library to satisfy the informational requirements of both intended and anticipated customers. According to Emaseah and Sunday (2016) and Osundina (1974), information resources accessibility is the situation that enables a student to access and get library items freely.

Statement of the Problem

Quality service delivery is seen as librarians providing specific products or services that fit their users' desires. It is seen in terms of bridging the gap between user expectations and the actual service provider. Studies have indicated that libraries often fall short in delivering quality services, reflected in the limited demand from patrons for existing library services (Obiora et al., 2020) in medical libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria. The low level of quality service delivery has been observed as an inconvenient environment in terms of library location and operation hours lack up-to-date equipment/facilities, and seating capacity of the library. Additionally, it includes being poorly attended to by individual clients, poor knowledge displayed in answering all clients, poor priority in responding to user queries, and delivery of user requests as promised. Inadequacies in types of resources, lack of usefulness of resources to medical students, the medical libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria, face significant challenges in delivering quality services to their users, resulting in unmet user expectations, inadequate access to relevant information, and poor user satisfaction (Lujan & Armando, 2017). It may be because the low levels of quality service delivery to clientele in medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria, could be solved through identified influence intervening independent variables.

User education has been identified as one of the tools for enhancing patrons' knowledge, skills, and abilities to use library resources and services efficiently. Librarians introduce and educate users to the complexity of university materials (Agyen, 2008; Bashorun et al., 2020). Information resources accessibility of patrons is another variable that could help in the use of collections and supplies to satisfy the informational needs of both intended and anticipated library customers (Usman, 2016). Though various studies have been conducted on the influences of resources on quality service delivery (Bappa, 2020), the researcher in this study was not aware of any studies carried out on the joint influence of users' education and information resource accessibility on quality service delivery to medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa State, Nigeria. Despite the critical importance of user education and information resource accessibility in facilitating quality service delivery, a thorough examination of the literature revealed a surprising lack of research focused on the joint influence of these factors on medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria. This study aims to address this knowledge gap. It was against this background that this study investigates the influence of user education, information resource accessibility, and quality service delivery in medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria.

Objective of the study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the influence of user education and information resource accessibility on quality service delivery of medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States Nigeria. However, the specific objectives of the study are to:

1. determine the influence of user education on quality service delivery of medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States Nigeria;
2. ascertain the influence of information resources accessibility on quality service delivery of medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria and
3. ascertain the joint influence of user education and information resources accessibility on quality service delivery to medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria.

Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses are formulated and will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- Ho1 User education has no significant influence on quality service delivery in medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States Nigeria;
- Ho2 Information resources accessibility has no significant influence on quality service delivery in medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria;
- Ho3 User education and information resources accessibility have no join influence on quality service delivery in medical university

Theoretical Framework

The Service Quality (SERVQUAL) model is developed by Parasuraman, Berry, and Zeithaml (1994) to assist employees in assessing their self-perception of the quality-of-service delivery. The SERVQUAL model is the most desirable feature for service providers' needs, as it assesses customer satisfaction as the top priority paradigm (Aghdaie & Faghani, 2012; Karim, 2020). The SERVQUAL model has addressed twenty-two (22) items to measure service delivery and five (5) constructs, such as assurance, tangibility, empathy, reliability, and responsiveness. This study adopted a convenient environment, removing tangibility, empathy, reliability, responsiveness, and assurance from the items, knowing the prompt crisis areas that Plateau and Nasarawa State

universities are facing to serve the purpose of addressing the problem of quality service delivery.

The theory assumes that a gap exists between customer expectations of quality service delivery and the perceived service delivery by the service provider. However, an observation is that customer interest should be the top priority in product and service delivery to maintain continuous client patronage. SERVQUAL was used to identify and meet differences in perceived user expectations (Parasuraman et al., 1994). Users of libraries in a particular workplace institution are thought to exploit service quality, which is defined as consumers' overall perception of the relative mastery of the organization and its services. To gain a competitive advantage over other institutions that may be providing the same services to the library, the medical student university libraries in the world, Plateau and Nasarawa States stand to do well in terms of academic excellence when strictly employing the principle involved with features of SERVQUAL.

Critique of SERVQUAL Model

The SERVQUAL model has faced criticism for its limitations as a measurement tool for assessing service quality. Specifically, empirical studies have identified a lack of discriminant validity between SERVQUAL's dimensions, while content validity remains uncertain due to overlapping conceptual definitions of some dimensions (Buttle, 1996; Polyakova & Mirza, 2015). Furthermore, the dimensions of 'empathy' and 'reliability' have been found to be confusing, with the reliability dimension overlapping with the technical quality offered by the Nordic model (Lapierre & Filiatrault, 1996; Polyakova & Mirza, 2015).

Relevance of this Theory to the Work

SERVQUAL model is crucial to the study since it compares client expectations with the results of a service or an item. The SERVQUAL model is relevant to the study because it measures staff preparedness to open libraries at the conformality of use and locate libraries where the environment is convenient. It puts physical equipment/facilities and staff and the service center in place for effective quality service delivery (tangibility). It also meets users' requests by providing free error resource service and prompt delivery of users' requests (reliability). The willingness to deliver and put extra effort into service delivery (responsiveness) Librarian sensitivity to users' needs and giving individual attention to users needs (empathy) All the dimensions ensured by librarians are the

efficient provision of quality service delivery to medical students in university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. Descriptive research design aims to observe all variables and subjects at one point without manipulating or controlling the subjects. According to Young (2016), descriptive design assesses people's attitudes or opinions towards situations, events, organizations, or procedures, using questionnaires, interviews, or direct observation to collect data. The total population of this study comprised 3,761 individuals from medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria. Taro Yamane was used for to arrive at a sample size of 361. Stratified random sampling technique was used in selecting the respondents. A structured and validated questionnaire was used for data collection, employing a five-style Likert scale table. The Cronbach alpha coefficient for the constructs ranged from 0.71 to 0.92, indicating that the instrument is highly reliable for data collection. Questionnaires are frequently used in survey research to collect quantitative data through a set of inquiries formulated for a specific study (Young, 2016). A total of 336 returned questionnaires represented a response rate of 93.07%. Data collected from the research instrument were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23. SPSS was used to analyze coded data responses, generating inferential statistics. Hypotheses were subjected to inferential statistics using single linear and multiple regression analyses.

Results

Hypothesis 1: user education has no significant influence on quality service delivery in medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria

Table 1: Test of Hypothesis One: Influence of user education on quality service delivery.

Variables	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	T	Sig	Adj.R ²	F(df)	ANOVA Sig.
(Constant)	36.760	3.148		11.676	.000	.323	40.918 (4,330)	.000
Library Orientation	.854	.160	.271	5.334	.000			
Library Tour	.696	.181	.208	3.850	.000			
Bibliography Instruction	.599	.191	.156	3.136	.002			
Virtual Talk	.664	.195	.174	3.397	.001			

Dependent Variable: Quality Service Delivery

Source: Researcher's Field work, 2024

Table 4.3.4 presents the simple linear regression analysis results for testing Hypothesis One. The regression model revealed that user education significantly predicts quality service delivery among medical students ($Adj.R^2=0.323$, $F(4, 330) = 40.92$, $p < 0.05$) The model indicated that 32.3% ($Adj.R^2= 0.323$) of the variation in quality service delivery is explained by user education. The results further revealed that library orientation ($\beta = 0.27$, $t(5.33) = 0.00$, $p < 0.05$), library tour ($\beta = 0.21$, $t(3.85) = 0.00$, $p < 0.05$), bibliographic instruction ($\beta = 0.16$, $t(3.14) = 0.00$, $p < 0.05$), and virtual talk ($\beta = 0.17$, $t(3.40) = 0.00$, $p < 0.05$) significantly influenced quality service delivery in medical libraries. Thus, the null hypothesis (H_{01} : user education has no significant influence on quality service delivery) is rejected. The findings suggest that medical university libraries that enhance user education, such as library orientation, library tour, bibliographic instruction, and virtual talk, will significantly boost quality service delivery among their students. The implication of the result is that the study's results can be replicated and generalized to other medical university libraries in Nigeria, providing insights for improving user education and quality service delivery nationwide.

Hypothesis 2: Information resources accessibility has no significant influence on quality service delivery in medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria.

Table 2: Test of Hypothesis Two: Influence of information accessibility on quality service delivery

Variables	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	T	Sig	Adj.R ²	F(df)	ANOVA Sig.
(Constant)	31.259	3.510		8.906	.000	.334	56.769 (3,331)	.000
Usefulness of Information Resources	.240	.072	.220	3.320	.001			
Types of Information Resources	.096	.073	.092	1.321	.188			
Access method of Information Resources	.371	.075	.335	4.971	.000			

Dependent Variable: Quality Service Delivery
Source: Researcher's Field work (2024)

Table 4.3.5 presents the simple linear regression analysis results for testing Hypothesis Two. The regression model revealed that user education significantly predicts quality service delivery. The results show that information resources accessibility ($Adj.R^2 = 0.334$, $F(3, 331) = 56.77$, $p < 0.05$) has a positive and significant influence on quality service delivery among medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria. This suggests that information resource accessibility could explain 33.4% ($Adj.R^2 = 0.334$) of the variations in quality service delivery in medical libraries. The results further revealed that the usefulness of information resources ($\beta = 0.22$, $t(3.32) = 0.00$, $p < 0.05$) and access method of information resources ($\beta = 0.34$, $t(4.97) = 0.00$, $p < 0.05$) had a statistically significant influence on quality service delivery. However, the type of information resources ($\beta = 0.09$, $t(1.32) = 0.00$, $p > 0.05$) did not have a significant influence. Hence, the null hypothesis (H_{02} : Information resources accessibility has no significant influence on quality service delivery) is rejected. These findings emphasize that providing accessible information resources among students will substantially enhance quality

service delivery, leading to better collaboration, communication, and overall efficiency in medical libraries' operations. The implication of the study is that information resources accessibility is crucial for quality service delivery in medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria. Library staff must prioritize providing accessible information resources to enhance quality service delivery. The study's results can be generalized to other medical libraries, providing insights for improving information resources accessibility and quality service delivery nationwide

Hypothesis Three: User education and information resources accessibility have no joint influence on quality service delivery in medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria.

Table 3: Influence of user education and information resources accessibility on quality service delivery

<i>Variables</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Beta (β)</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>Sig</i>	<i>Adj.R²</i>	<i>F(df)</i>	<i>ANOV A Sig.</i>
(Constant)	27.672	3.483		7.944	.000	.374	29.451(7,327)	.000
Library Orientation	.547	.165	.174	3.322	.001			
Library Tour	.404	.183	.121	2.204	.028			
Bibliography Instruction	.168	.202	.044	.831	.406			
Virtual Talk	.350	.198	.092	1.770	.078			
Usefulness of Information Resources	.146	.075	.134	1.958	.051			
Types of Information Resources	.040	.072	.038	.554	.580			
Access method of Information Resources	.243	.077	.220	3.147	.002			

Dependent Variable: Quality Service Delivery

Source: Researcher's Field work (2024)

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The result in Table 4.3.6 presents the multiple regression analysis results examining Hypothesis Three. The result revealed that user education and information resources accessibility had a joint significant influence on quality service delivery ($Adj.R^2 = 0.374$, $F(7, 333) = 29.45$, $p < 0.05$) in medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria. This confirms that user education and information resources accessibility jointly influence quality service delivery in medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria. The model suggests that user education and information resources accessibility can explain 37.4% ($Adj.R^2 = 0.374$) of the variations in quality service delivery in medical libraries, confirming the model's reliability. The results further revealed that library orientation ($\beta = 0.17$, $t(333) = 3.32$, $p < 0.05$), library tour ($\beta = 0.12$, $t(333) = 2.20$, $p < 0.05$), and access method of information resources ($\beta = 0.22$, $t(333) = 3.15$, $p < 0.05$) had a statistically significant influence on quality service delivery. However, the results also showed that bibliographic instruction ($\beta = 0.04$, $t(333) = 0.83$, $p < 0.05$) virtual talk ($\beta = 0.09$, $t(333) = 1.77$, $p < 0.05$) usefulness of information resources ($\beta = 0.13$, $t(333) = 1.96$, $p < 0.05$), and types of information resources ($\beta = 0.38$, $t(333) = 0.55$, $p < 0.05$) did not significantly influence quality service delivery in medical libraries. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{03}) is rejected. Overall, these results highlight the importance of teaching user education and information resources accessibility to enhance quality service delivery in medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria. The implication to the study's results can be generalized to other medical libraries, providing insights for improving user education and information resources accessibility to enhance quality service delivery nationwide.

Implications of Findings

Despite these limitations, the findings of this study revealed that the level of quality service delivery of students in medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria was high. Similarly, the level of quality service delivery of library staff in medical university libraries in Plateau and Nasarawa States, Nigeria was also high. These findings imply that, despite the limitations of the SERVQUAL model, it can still provide valuable insights into the quality of service delivery in specific contexts, such as medical university libraries in Nigeria. However, it is essential to consider the limitations of the SERVQUAL model when interpreting these findings. Future studies should explore alternative models or frameworks that can provide a more nuanced and accurate assessment of service quality in medical university libraries.

Conclusion

The study concluded that user education and information resources accessibility are key contributors to quality service delivery. The hypotheses findings revealed that user education and information resources accessibility have a significant and positive influence on quality service delivery. User education and information resources accessibility had a combined significant influence on quality service delivery. It is part of the key importance for improving quality service delivery to medical students. Medical university libraries must be encouraged to obtain accurate and timely services consequently, users' education and information resources accessibility were necessary knowledge that could assist library staff to help medical students to carry out the required information in their studies in the university libraries.

Recommendations:

Library management should strategize on how librarians can effectively deliver user education to users in the library. The importance of placing high priority on bibliographic instruction and virtual talks for medical students cannot be overstated. Understanding the knowledge to be gained can have a significant and positive impact on users' studies.

Library management should prioritize library staff training to ensure they understand the significant and positive impact of delivering accessible information resources to medical students, particularly in terms of the types of information resources provided.

The study also recommends that librarians recognize the key factors contributing to high-quality service delivery in medical university libraries, specifically user education and information resources accessibility. To achieve this, librarians should focus on improving bibliographic instruction, the usefulness of resources, and the types of resources provided. The combined influence of these two independent variables on the dependent variable can yield a positive and significant impact on the lives of library users.

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